

Futuristic Traces in Quranic Verses

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ABSTRACT

There are verses in the Quran that may be considered as futuristic, in the sense that their contents could be reflecting scientific and technical information of the future. Possible Quranic references to the matters such as, homogeneity principles, relativity of time, dark energy and dark matter, and some other relevant subjects will be discussed in this article. Some of these futuristic verses even seem to contain predictions about the cosmic evolution and fate of the universe. In particular, contrary to the present leanings of the astrophysicists towards an ever-expanding universe, Quran seems to predict a closed universe. This projected fate for the universe appears even more interesting in view of the very recent observations of a weakening dark energy which makes the big-crunch a more likely scenario. Quran also appears to forecast birth of a new universe, following demise of the current one, in which the promised Resurrection will arise. Upcoming signs of the Resurrection Day, as pictured by the Quran, also seem to match scientifically predicted events in the course of cosmic evolution.

Keywords: Quran, homogeneity, relativity, dark matter, dark energy, big bang, resurrection

Introduction

Quran frequently speaks of signs of God by addressing the natural phenomena, although some of these addresses seem to have been made in a tone appropriate to understandings of those living in the revelation era. In this article it is tried to show that some of the Quranic verses can also be explained from contemporary scientific perspectives.

The suggested interpretations in this article offer possible alternative readings for a number of verses that show compatibility with contemporary knowledge. However, interpreting these verses from contemporary perspectives should not be considered as disregarding their traditional interpretations, but only as complementary. These contemporary perspectives will be presented in different fields such as, physics, astrophysics, geology, etc.

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Verse 41:53, forecasts recognition of the Quran's truthfulness by future spectators:

سنريهم آياتنا في الآفاق وفي أنفسهم حتى يتبين لهم أنه الحق² أولم يكف بربك أنه على كل شيء شهيد

Translation² [1]:

We will show them Our signs in the universe and within themselves until it becomes clear to them that this 'Quran' is the truth. Is it not enough that your Lord is a Witness over all things? **41:53**

However, before entering the topics, it would be helpful to begin with a brief summary of the birth, evolution, and fate of the universe, as is understood today and as it pertains to the subject matters of this article.

Birth and evolution of the universe

The prevalent scenario is that the universe was born 13.8 billion years ago, out of the sudden expansion (Big Bang) of an initial state of extremely high density and high temperature [2,3]. In the continuing expansion ensuing this event, the universe has grown to its present inconceivable vastness. Countless, extremely small to extremely large, potential formations of mass and energy have come to existence since the Big Bang, each to follow its course of evolution and demise (Fig.1).

Fig.1 A pictorial featuring of the cosmic birth and evolution [4]

On the grand scale in the cosmic evolution these formations include, among other things, immeasurable number of galaxies and stars. But contrary to its birth, fate of the universe remains much more speculative. Presently main theories predict that the universe will either collapse back

² Translation of the verses in this article are quoted from *Quran.com* [1]

on itself (Big Crunch) or through two other scenarios, Big Freeze and Big Rip (Fig.2), will expand forever [5]. Although astrophysicists are not sure about the fate of the universe, but presently they are leaned towards an ever-expanding Big Freeze scenario. According to this scenario universe eventually becomes infinitely vast, dark, and cold; surely a grim fate!

Fig.2 Three main scenarios suggested for birth, evolution, and possible fates of the universe [5]

The uncertainties in these predictions mainly come from the unknown physics and future evolution of two mysterious dark entities in the universe, **dark matter** and **dark energy**. Dark matter by 27% and dark energy by 68%, constitute an overwhelming 95% of the mass-energy content of the universe, whereas all of the visible universe that we can see or detect via electromagnetic radiation accounts for only 5% of this content [6]. These entities are called “dark” because they are invisible and undetectable by light, but can only be detected through their gravitational effects. In a nutshell, *dark matter gives the galaxies extra mass they need to stay intact while dark energy accelerates the expansion of the universe* [7]. Dark matter has appeared some 400 million years after the Big

Bang, and dark energy has begun to intervene in cosmic affairs, some 10 billion years after the Big Bang (Fig.1). As of yet, physics of both these dark entities are unknown but there are speculations that, somehow, they may be related to the blackholes which themselves are among mysteries of the universe [8, 9]. Super blackholes have been detected in the centers of the galaxies with huge masses, orders of magnitude greater than the Sun, but with much smaller dimensions. Even light in close vicinity of the blackholes cannot escape their enormous gravity and no light comes off them either. Being as such, blackholes also look dark and in this sense, they too may be considered among the dark entities in the universe.

The solar system

The solar system (also Earth) was born out of a swirling clump of interstellar dust, 4.6 billion years ago [10]. The Sun itself is predicted to swell up and turn into a “red giant” some 5 billion years from now, most probably engulfing even Earth’s orbit. Eventually the Sun will turn into a white dwarf which is a dead star that has exhausted all its burnable nuclear fuel. Sun will slowly cool down to very low temperatures which is a typical final state for low-mass stars. Actually, all stars in the universe will eventually die and turn dark and cool [11, 12]. As for the Earth, the red giant Sun will most probably engulf it, but even if this doesn’t happen in its final phases of existence, remaining atmosphere and ocean waters of Earth will be vanished and boiled away.

Topics of relevance to the subject matter of this article along with their related Quranic verses will now be presented.

Homogeneity of space and time

Physics is the frontier science in understanding of the material world and of fundamental importance in physics are the homogeneity principles:

“It is a fundamental assumption in modern physics that space and time are both homogeneous. The homogeneity of space and time is reflected in the spacetime translation invariance of natural laws, and it ensures that the same experiment performed at two different places or repeated at two different times gives the same result” [13]. Stated in other words:

Homogeneity of space: Laws of physics are valid anywhere.

Homogeneity of time: Laws of physics are valid anytime.

Without these principles no physical law can be defined and as a result, no instrument can be guaranteed to work as intended and no physical event will ever be (computationally) predictable; a total chaos!

Verses 3 and 4 of chapter 67 are quite expressive regarding these principles:

الذي خلق سبع سماوات طباقاً^٣ ما ترى في خلق الرحمن من تفاوت^٤ فارجع البصر هل ترى من فطور 67:3

ثم ارجع البصر كرتين ينقلب إليك البصر خاسئاً وهو حسير 67:4

Translations:

He is the One⁷ Who created seven heavens, one above the other, you will not see any difference in creation of the Most Compassionate, so, look again, do you see any break in His creation. **67:3**

Then turn your vision again, and then again; in the end your vision will come back to you, worn out and frustrated (after having failed to find any difference). **67:4**

The Arabic word ترى “you see” in 67:3 can represent the act of “physical observation” which is necessary to discover the laws of the nature, and البصر ”the eye” can represent the “instrument of observation”. As such, the verse implies that observations yield same results everywhere and show no difference (تفاوت) in the laws of creation (laws of physics), even after repeating the observation (the experiment) in a later time. In verse 67:4, repeatability of the observation results in time, again and again, is re-emphasized. From a modern physics point of view:

Verse 67:3 expresses homogeneities of both space and time, while verse 67:4 specifically re-emphasizes homogeneity of time.

Mysterious dark actors of the universe

Throughout the Quran, there are many verses in which God is mentioned as the Sole Creator of the heavens and the Earth. Verse 6:1 is the first of these verses³, and quite peculiarly, in this verse after stating creation of the universe, a puzzling subsequent creation of the **darknesses and light** is also added:

الحمد لله الذي خلق السماوات والأرض وجعل الظلمات والنور ثم الذين كفروا بربهم يعدلون **6:1**

Translation:

All praise is for Allah alone, Who created the heavens and the Earth, **and brought into being darknesses and light**, and yet those who have rejected the call of the Truth ascribe others to be equals to their Lord **6:1**

Dark matter and dark energy were briefly mentioned in the introduction of this article as being the two major actors of the universe. In the followings, it is explained why “the darknesses” in 6:1, may well be referring to these enigmatic entities of the universe.

1) Joint occurrences of “the darknesses” and “the light” can be seen in a total of 10 verses in the Quran⁴, but except in 6:1, in all other 9 verses “the darknesses” symbolizes disbelief and wrong doings, whereas “the light” symbolizes guidance. What makes verse 6:1 exceptionally different from other 9 verses is that: ***In 6:1 “the darknesses and the light” are mentioned in the context of physical creation of the universe (not symbolizing disbelief and guidance). This implies that, in 6:1, “the darknesses and the light” are also physical entities, just as “the heavens and the Earth” are physical entities in this verse.***

³ In fact, 6:1 is the 4th verse in which creation of the universe is mentioned, but it is the first verse in which God is explicitly introduced as the subject pronoun of the creation.

⁴(2:257), (5:16), (**6:1**), (13:16), (14:1), (14:5), (33:43), (35:20), (57:9), (65:11)

2) The Arabic verb خلق “created” refers to the original creation of anything, while the verb جعل “brought into being” refers to a simultaneous or subsequent creation made within the original creation. Similarly, in the cosmic evolution, dark matter and dark energy both showed up some time after the Big Bang (Fig.1), which justifies using the verb جعل (subsequent creation) after the verb خلق (original creation) in this verse.

3) Even if we accept it as being physical, “the darkneses” in 6:1 may be suspected as simply referring to the dark background observable in the night sky, and not necessarily to some real physical entities. But if this were to be the case, since the darkness in the night sky appears as a “single” continuous background, the verse should have referred to it in singular “darkness”, and not in plural form “darkneses”. This can imply that *in 6:1, Quran is not simply referring to the dark background which is observable in the night sky, but is referring to some other physical dark entities.*

4) Finally, in the Quran “heavens” (the universe) is always mentioned before “the Earth” (see for instance, 6:1) which is justifiable, because heavens are by far greater than the Earth alone. Similarly, in terms of the mass-energy content, dark constituents of the universe are by far greater than its visible constituents (95% vs 5%). So, it is also reasonable that in verse 6:1, “the darkneses” or the much greater invisible portion of the universe be mentioned before “the light”, which represents the much smaller visible portion of the universe.

Considering the above justifications, a physical interpretation of the verse 6:1, in par with the current understandings of the dark matter and dark energy, can be:

The physical universe is composed of two distinct “invisible” (الظلمات) and “visible” (النور) portions:

“Dark matter, dark energy (blackholes?)” make up the “invisible” portion of the universe.

“Stars and all other by-light detectable entities” make up the “visible” portion of the universe.

There are also two other interesting verses in the Quran that may well be referring to the greatest invisible actor of the universe; **the invisible dark energy.**

Invisible Pillars holding up the firmament

It was mentioned in the introduction that the invisible dark energy which makes up 68% of the total mass-energy content of the universe, keeps the universe from gravitational collapse by its expanding force which accelerates the cosmic growth. Verses 13:2 and 31:10, are both very interesting in this respect:

الله الذي رفع السماوات بغير عمد ترونها^{ثم} استوى على العرش^{ثم} وسخر الشمس والقمر^{لكل} يجري لأجل مسمى^٥ يدبر 13:2
الأمر يفصل الآيات لعلكم بقاء ربكم توقنون

خلق السماوات بغير عمد ترونها^{ثم} وألقى في الأرض رواسي أن تُميد بكم وبث فيها من كل دابة^٥ وأنزلنا من السماء ماء 31:10
فأنبتنا فيها من كل زوج كريم

Translations:

It is Allah Who has raised the heavens without any supports that you could see, and then He established Himself on the Throne (of Dominion). And He it is Who has made the Sun and the Moon subservient (to a law), each running its course till an appointed term. He governs the entire order of the universe and clearly explains the signs that you may be firmly convinced about meeting your Lord 13:2

He created the heavens without any pillars visible to you and He placed mountains in the Earth as pegs lest it should turn topsy turvy with you, and He dispersed all kinds of animals over the Earth, and sent down water from the sky causing all kinds of excellent plants to grow on it 31:10

An important point that should be noted in these verses is that, there was no need in both these verses to add “**that you could see**” or “**visible to you**” (تَرَوْنَهَا). In fact, it was quite sufficient to only say “Allah raised heavens with no pillars ...”. Nevertheless, in both these verses Quran emphasizes on invisibility of the holding pillars by adding terms like, “that you could see” or “visible to you”, which implies that: ***There are some pillars which hold up the firmament, but they are invisible to you!***

Considering our present knowledge of the dark energy and its role in countering the gravitational attraction⁵, here “***invisible pillars***” can easily be replaced by “***invisible dark energy***”, the ***invisible entity which through its expansion-causing force prevents galaxies from collapsing onto each other and in effect “holds up the firmament”!***

Cosmic radiation and meteors “the devils”

Stars are said in the Quran to follow and deflect the “devils”, while comets are also said to burn the “devils” with blazing fire!

The following verses are notable in this respect:

إنا زينا السماء الدنيا بزينة الكواكب 37:6

وحفظا من كل شيطان مارد 37:7

لا يسمعون إلى الملا الأعلى ويقذفون من كل جانب 37:8

دحورا^{ثم} ولهم عذاب واصب 37:9

إلا من خطف الخطفة فاتبعه شهاب ثاقب 37:10

⁵ “Invisible pillars” has been interpreted by some to be the gravity, ignoring that gravity causes fall, not rise!

ولقد زينا السماء الدنيا بمصابيح وجعلناها رجوما للشياطين ؕ وأعدنا لهم عذاب السعير_ 67:5

Translations:

Indeed, We have adorned the lowest heaven with the stars for decoration 37:6

and for protection from every rebellious devil 37:7

They cannot listen to the Upper Realm and are hit from every side 37:8

Repulsed, for they are under a perpetual penalty, 37:9

And if any is able to snatch a fragment, he is pursued by a piercing flame 37:10

And We have certainly beautified the nearest heaven with lamps [i.e., stars] and have made [from] them what is thrown at the devils and have prepared for them the punishment of the Blaze 67:5

These verses have been referred to by some critics of the Quran as being nonscientific, but there can be a different interpretation if here the word **“devils” be taken as a metaphoric substitute for outer space “things” that endanger life on Earth**. Cosmic rays and meteoroids represent the two main dangers in this respect [14, 15], and if this be the case, there are also two effective natural mechanisms that protect humans against these dangers: **Earth’s magnetic field** and **Earth’s atmosphere** [16, 17].

Cosmic rays

Cosmic rays are composed of high energy (mostly ionized and to a lesser degree neutral) particles that originate from different sources in the space (including from the Sun).

Ionized cosmic rays are primarily deflected by Earth’s magnetic field, but **it is Earth’s rotation that is chiefly responsible for generating its magnetic field** [18], **a rotation that is reflected in circular motion of the stars, as perceived by those on Earth** (Fig.3).

Fig.3 The apparent motion of stars in the night sky due to Earth's rotation [19]

Quran is calling the “moving stars” the “devil deflectors”, as an indirect reference to the rotation-generated magnetic field of the Earth. This magnetic field deflects harmful “cosmic rays” which in metaphoric language of the Quran have been called, “the devils”!

This deflection mechanism is continuously at work, and the word “perpetual” in 37:9 may be hinting at the continuity of this action.

Meteoroids

Earth’s atmosphere not only participates in scattering and diffusing cosmic rays, but it also burns almost all (90 to 95 percent) of meteors⁶ before they can reach the ground [20]. Other mostly high-speed neutral rays and objects which have penetrated through the magnetic barrier of the Earth, will be deflected or burned by Earth’s atmosphere. Here, *Quran describes “meteors” as “devils” that have escaped the magnetic barrier (37:10), but will be eradicated by the second defensive mechanism which is burning in the atmosphere.* Symbolically, the trailing flame behind the burning meteors during their entrance in the atmosphere has been likened in the Quran to a “piercing flame” that obliterates the intruders.

It is notable here, that the Arabic word السماء or “the lowest heaven” which has been used in verse 67:5, seems to have been used in the Quran to represent, from Earth’s atmosphere to the entire universe (e.g., 37:6, 43:11, 50:9, 16:79).

Day(s) in the Quran

In addition to its common meaning as a 24-hour period, the word “day” also seems to have other meanings in the Quran. Both in singular and in plural forms, “day” has also been used as specified or unspecified, equal or unequal periods of time. The word “day” has also been used in the Quran as “when”, often in reference to the Resurrection Day. Examples for different usages will be shown in the followings.

Relativistic Days

Relativistic notions of time can be seen in some verses in the Quran and two of the most prominent such verses speak explicitly of time dilation associated with the motion, in agreement with the theory of relativity [20]. In these verses dilations of the “day” (time) can be observed:

32:5 يدبر الأمر من السماء إلى الأرض ثم يعرج إليه في يوم كان مقداره ألف سنة مما تعدون

70:4 تعرج الملائكة والروح إليه في يوم كان مقداره خمسين ألف سنة

He conducts every affair from the heavens to the Earth, then it all ascends to Him on a Day whose length is a thousand years by your counting **32:5**

The angels and the Spirit [i.e., Gabriel] will ascend to Him during a Day the extent of which is fifty thousand years **70:4**

⁶ Terminology [18]:

Meteoroid, before entering the atmosphere

Meteor, while passing through the atmosphere

Meteorite, when reached ground

Regardless of the metaphoric interpretations of these verses and that angels are usually considered to be metaphysical beings not bounded by physical laws, relativistic parallels in the physical world can easily be conceived for these verses:

Firstly, in relativity time dilation happens when there is a relative motion, and in both these verses time dilations are associated with a relative motion.

Secondly, in Relativity the amount of time dilation is not fixed (depends on the relative velocities). In these verses too, the amount of time dilations is not fixed and varies (50,000, 1000 years, or else!).

Thirdly, and more interestingly, shorter passage of time in these verses has been associated with the moving ones and longer passage of time has been associated with the stationary ones on Earth (32:5) which again is in exact agreement with Relativity.

From a modern Physics perspective, verses 32:5 and 70:4 accurately portray characteristics of the overly proven Eistein's Special theory of Relativity.

It can be seen here, that in the Quran "day" can represent "any length of time", and not necessarily a common day, a point that will soon become clearer.

Days as different time periods

Three verses in chapter 41 together with verse 50:38, may better clarify some other meanings of "day" (يوم) in the Quran:

قل أنتم لتكفرون بالذي خلق الأرض في يومين وتجعلون له أندادا^٤ ذلك رب العالمين 41:9

وجعل فيها رواسي من فوقها وبارك فيها وقدر فيها أقواتها في أربعة أيام سواء للسانين 41:10

ثم استوى إلى السماء وهي دخان فقال لها وللأرض ائتيا طوعا أو كرها قالتا أتينا طائعين 41:11

فقضاهن سبع سماوات في يومين وأوحى في كل سماء أمرها^٥ وزينا السماء الدنيا بمصابيح وحفظا^٦ ذلك تقدير العزيز العليم

ولقد خلقنا السماوات والأرض وما بينهما في ستة أيام وما مسنا من لغوب 50:38

Translations:

Say, "Do you indeed disbelieve in He who created the Earth in two days and attribute to Him equals? That is the Lord of the worlds." 41:9

He set on the (Earth), mountains standing firm, high above it, and bestowed blessings on the Earth, and measure therein all things to give them nourishment in due proportion, in four Days, in accordance with (the needs of) those who seek (Sustenance). 41:10

Moreover, He comprehended in His design the sky, *and it had been (as) smoke*: He said to it and to the Earth: "Come ye together, willingly or unwillingly." They said: "We do come (together), in willing obedience." 41:11

So He completed them as seven firmaments *in two Days*, and He assigned to each heaven its duty and command. And We adorned the lower heaven with lights, and (provided it) with guard. Such is the Decree of (Him) the Exalted in Might, Full of Knowledge. **41:12**

We created the heavens and the Earth and all that is between them *in six days*, and weariness did not even touch Us. **50:38**

A cosmic day of 2.27 billion years

There are seven verses in the Quran wherein the universe is said to have been created in 6 days, but in one verse (41:9) it is stated that the Earth was created in 2 days. As it was mentioned before, the universe is 13.8 billion years old, while the Earth (solar system) is 4.56 billion years old and the ratio of 13.8 to 4.56 (ignoring small uncertainties in their estimates) is almost exactly 3, which is amazingly the same as 6/2, stated in the Quran! This by itself shows a striking example of the scientific accuracy of the Quran. However, as far as lengths and ratios are concerned, why Quran did not state that the Earth was created in one day and the universe was created in three days, which preserves the ratio 3, as before? Could this Quranic “day” of 2.27 billion years long (4.56/2) be a “**cosmic day**”, probably associated with an as yet unknown periodic cosmic-event?

A rotating universe?

As a unit of time and in its original meaning, “day” is defined to be the period of one complete cycle of the planet Earth around its axis of rotation. The question is, in par with this rotation-related definition of a day, could Quran be referring to the above defined “**cosmic day**” as the period of some cyclic cosmic rotation? A cosmic day of 2.27 billion years duration may be related to some sort of universal rotation, and the simplest imaginable such rotation is rotation of the universe itself.

In spite of the absence of observational evidence so far, the concept of a rotating universe has been evoked by some renowned scientists such as George Gamow, Kurt Godel, and Stephen Hawking [22-24]. Some theoretical models have even computed values up to 10^{-9} radian/year⁷ for angular velocity of the universe [23, 26].

In the simplest case, if it be assumed that the universe makes a complete rotation every 2.27 billion years (duration of a Quranic cosmic day), then angular velocity of the universe can be computed as⁸:

$$\frac{2\pi}{2.27 \times 10^9 (\text{year})} = 2.8 \times 10^{-9} \text{ radian/year}$$

It is very interesting that this number rests reasonably close to the highest end of the above-mentioned theoretical estimates for rotation of the universe. It is also interesting that verse 21:104 which will soon be discussed, describes evolution of the universe as being similar to rolling of a scroll, and rolling of a scroll is always associated with rotation!

⁷ Equivalent to a complete rotation of the universe, every one billion years

⁸ A complete cycle corresponds to 2π radian rotation

Days as Geologic Eons

The followings are quoted from [27]:

“The geologic time scale is a system used by scientists to describe Earth's history in terms of major geological or paleontological events (such as the formation of a new rock layer or the appearance or demise of certain lifeforms). ***Geologic time spans are divided into units and subunits, the largest of which are eons... and there are 4 eons:***

Hadean: The oldest of the geologic eons is the Hadean, which began about 4.6 billion years ago with the formation of Earth and ended about 4 billion years ago with the appearance of the first single-celled organisms...

Archean: The next geologic eon, the Archean, began about 4 billion years ago. During this period, the cooling of the Earth's crust allowed for the formation of the first oceans and continents...

Proterozoic: The Proterozoic eon began about 2.5 billion years ago and ended about 500 million years ago when the first complex lifeforms appeared. During this period, the Great Oxygenation Event transformed the Earth's atmosphere, allowing for the evolution of aerobic organisms...

Phanerozoic: The most recent geologic eon is the Phanerozoic, which began about 540 million years ago. This eon is very distinct from the previous three—the Hadean, Archean, and Proterozoic—which are sometimes known as the Precambrian era...”

Verse 41:10 may well be referring to the four major geological eons of the Earth as “four days”, but 4 days with unequal lengths (600, 1500, 1960, and 540 million years).

During these four periods Earth has been transformed from its initial lifeless, to its present balanced habitable state. Verse 41:10, describes these “stages needed for preparation life on Earth” as “measure therein all things to give them nourishment in due proportion”.

Ordinance of the heavens in two days

Verse 41:12 describes an ambiguous act of “ordinance of the heavens” (different from act of creation) during some undefined length of time referred to as, “2 days”. *These “2 days” may be referring to two (even very short) critical periods in the beginnings of the cosmic evolution (Fig.1), during which some fundamental laws (of physics) might have been implemented in the universe.*

It is also notable that like in verse 37:6, verse 41:12 emphasizes that the lower heaven (sky) is the one containing the stars, implying again that the visible universe in spite of its astonishing enormity may only be the least of the heavens.

The nebular hypothesis

Although in verse 41:11 there is no mention of the word “day”, it contains an interesting description of Earth’s creation from a “nebula” (Fig.3), and this can qualify 41:11 as a futuristic verse which will be understood but long after revelation of the Quran.

The following quotation describes a nebula [28]:

“The **nebular hypothesis** is the most widely accepted model in the field of cosmogony to explain the formation and evolution of the Solar System (as well as other planetary systems). It suggests the Solar System is formed from gas and dust orbiting the Sun which clumped up together to form the planets...

According to the nebular theory, stars form in massive and dense clouds of molecular hydrogen—giant molecular clouds (GMC). These clouds are gravitationally unstable, and matter coalesces within them to smaller denser clumps, which then rotate, collapse, and form stars. Star formation is a complex process, which always produces a gaseous protoplanetary disk (proplyd) around the young star. This may give birth to planets in certain circumstances, which are not well known. Thus, the formation of planetary systems is thought to be a natural result of star formation. A Sun-like star usually takes approximately 1 million years to form, with the protoplanetary disk evolving into a planetary system over the next 10–100 million years.”

The solar system has formed from a circling cloud of dust and gas called nebula, which can best be resembled by a body of smoke (Fig.3), just as is described in verse 41:11.

Fig.4 Trifid Nebula, showing its complex gas and plasma (smoke like) structure [29]

Armageddon and Resurrection Day

According to the Quran, there will be two momentous events with crucial importance for mankind: Armageddon (Apocalypse) which is termination of all lives, and Resurrection which is revival of the dead for the Judgement. The dates of these two grave events are said to be known only to God, but they will be announced by “the first” and “the second” blowing of the “trumpet”:

ونفخ في الصور فصعق من في السماوات ومن في الأرض إلا من شاء الله ثم نفخ فيه أخرى فإذا هم قيام ينظرون **39:68**

Translation:

The Trumpet will be blown and all those in the heavens and all those on the Earth will fall dead, except those Allah wills 'to spare'. Then it will be blown again and they will rise up at once, looking on 'in anticipation'. **39:68**

From (39:68), it is not clear if Resurrection will happen immediately after Armageddon or with a time gap, however, it seems from the following verses that there may be a huge time gap between death and resurrection of humans:

يوم يدعوك فتستجيبون بحمده وتظنون إن لبثتم إلا قليلا **17:52**

كأنهم يوم يرونها لم يلبثوا إلا عشية أو ضحاها **79:46**

On the Day He will call you, you will 'instantly' respond by praising Him, thinking you had remained 'in the world' only for a little while **17:52**

On the Day they see it, it will be as if they had stayed 'in the world' no more than one evening or its morning **79:46**

These and several other similar verses could be suggesting that the time between death and resurrection is so long that in comparison, human lifetimes on Earth will seem too short. This can equally imply that the time between Armageddon and Resurrection should also be very long. Affected by human egoism, some might think that ending of the mankind (Armageddon) should coincide with ending of the universe. But creation of man is said in the Quran to be by far inferior to creation of the universe (and all superior beings that might exist in it), a fact that only now can better be understood:

لخلق السماوات والأرض أكبر من خلق الناس ولكن أكثر الناس لا يعلمون **40:57**

أأنتم أشد خلقا أم السماء بناها **79:27**

Translations:

The creation of the heavens and Earth is greater by far than the creation of mankind, though most people do not know it. **40:57**

Are you a more difficult creation or is the heaven? He [i.e., Allāh] constructed it. **79:27**

The universe has existed billions of years before any man has ever walked on Earth and it will continue its course of evolution many billions of years after demise of the mankind. But, regardless of when Armageddon and Resurrection might be, and irrespective of what the dead may or may not experience between their death and resurrection, a question can be asked:

What does Quran predict for the cosmic events up until the Resurrection, and to what extent these predicted events match our current knowledge of the cosmic evolution?

Quran describes the cosmic events up until Resurrection, not necessarily in chronological order, but often as dispersed events leading to the Resurrection Day. These are usually stated by saying, “the day” or “when”, such and such events will take place.

Quran’s view of the cosmic birth and evolution

There are verses in the Quran that describe cosmic events throughout the life of the universe, but perhaps the most prominent verse that describes creation of the universe from the start to its end, and from its end to the Resurrection Day, is verse 21:104. However, its preceding verse should also be noted in this connection, because it shows that the stated “day” in 21:104, is identical with the “day” mentioned in 21:103, both referring to the Resurrection Day:

لا يحزنهم الفزع الأكبر وتتلقاهم الملائكة هذا يومكم الذي كنتم توعدون **21:103**
يوم نظوي السماء كطي السجل للكتب^٢ كما بدأنا أول خلق نعيده^٣ وعدا علينا^٤ إنا كنا فاعلين **21:104**

Translations:

The Hour of the Great Terror shall not grieve them, and the angels shall receive them saying: "**This is your Day** which you had been promised." **21:103**

On that Day, We shall roll up the skies as a writer rolls up [his] scrolls. We shall reproduce creation just as We produced it the first time: this is Our binding promise. We shall certainly do all these things. **21:104**

Although the “day” mentioned in verse 21:104 is identical with the “day” mentioned in verse 21:103, a distinction can be noted. The “day” in 21:103 is the exact Resurrection Day (with an exact date), whereas the “day” in 21:104 actually comprises a sequence of cosmic events, culminating in the Resurrection Day.

Verse 21:104, briefly states that sometime in the future the sky (universe) will begin to contract, similar to a scroll when it is being rolled up. The final result of this contraction will of course be a “folded scroll”, a compact state of matter, just like state of the universe before or at the Big Bang. The verse continues by saying that, at this stage of contraction another creation will be initiated just like the previous creation, which can mean ignition of another Big Bang and creation of another universe, just like creation of the present universe.

Since the word “Day” in the beginning of verse 21:103 is identical with the “Day” mentioned in 21:104, it can be interpreted that at some stage in the cosmic evolution of the “newborn universe”, the Resurrection Day will be held in it.

In spite of its brevity, verse 21:104 may be regarded as an iconic verse in the Quran, because of its colossal cosmological implications.

Verse 21:104 describes not only creation of the universe to have started from a compact state, but also implies its following expansion and its final contraction. This verse is also indicative of the subsequent creation of another universe in the same manner that the present universe was created. Apparently, it is in this newborn universe that at some stage in its cosmic evolution, the promised Resurrection Day will be convened.

In fact, to emphasize the concept of an initially compressed and subsequently expanding universe, Quran in verses 21:30 and 51:47, both consistent with verse 21:104, describes the same process:

أولم ير الذين كفروا أن السماوات والأرض كانتا رتقا ففتقناهما^{٣٠} وجعلنا من الماء كل شيء حي^{٣١} أفلا يؤمنون **21:30**
 والسماء بنيناها بأيدٍ وإنا لموسعون **51:47**

Translations:

Do the disbelievers realize not that the heavens and Earth were 'once' one mass then We split them apart? And We created from water every living thing. Will they not then believe? **21:30**

We built the universe with 'great' might, and We are certainly expanding 'it'. **51:47**

It can be seen that, in exact agreement with 21:104,

The initial compactness and subsequent expansion of the universe is also expressed in 21:30.

The ongoing expansion of the universe is clearly indicated in 51:47.

There are also several similar-content verses in the Quran that, in general, state repeating of the creation. The following is an example:

الله يبدأ الخلق ثم يعيده ثم إليه ترجعون **30:11**

God brings creation into being; in the end He will reproduce it and it is to Him you will be recalled. **30:11**

As was mentioned before, another interesting implication of the scroll similitude in verse 21:104, can be possible rotation of the universe, because unfolding and folding of a scroll always requires rotating of the scroll.

As another observation regarding the scroll similitude in 21:104, it is notable that majority (60%) of the galaxies in the universe are spiral in shape [30], much like semi open scrolls (Fig.4).

Fig.5 Examples of spiral galaxies [31]

Finally, if Resurrection is to be held in another upcoming universe, then obviously both the universe and the Earth in that universe should be different from the present Earth and present universe (even laws of physics may somehow be different in the new universe). Interestingly, verse 14:48 seems to support this expectation:

14:48 يوم تبدل الأرض غير الأرض والسموات وبرزوا لله الواحد القهار

Translation:

(Do warn them of the) Day when the heavens and the Earth shall be altogether changed; when all will appear fully exposed before Allah, the One, the Irresistible **14:48**

The enormous interval between the Armageddon and Resurrection Day (possibly, billions of years!) seems to be unbelievably long, but this may be due to the very short life span of humans compared to the cosmic time scales. Actually, the dead may have little or no sense of the time elapsed between their death and resurrection, be it thousands or billions of years. Verses (70:6) and (70:7) are also noteworthy in comparing human time scales with that of The Almighty God. In anticipation of the Resurrection Day, it is said in the Quran:

They see it far off (**70:6**), and We see it near (**70:7**)

Fate of the universe

A fascinating point in verse 21:104, is its prediction of the fate of the universe. It can be seen that in comparison with possible fates shown in Fig.1, Quran is clearly pointing to a closed universe scenario (Big Crunch), a universe that finally collapses and returns back to its initial compact state:

Contrary to the present belief held by the majority of astrophysicists which supports an ever-expanding universe, Quran clearly predicts a closed universe.

As it was said in the introduction, dark energy is the force behind the accelerating expansion of the universe and it has started to act some 10 billion years after the Big Bang (Fig.1). However, by the same token, it is also possible that at some stage in the future, dark energy draws back and reverses the entire course of cosmic evolution. But in fact, this process might have already started!

Recently, in early 2025, the news has come out that based on numerous observations, dark energy may indeed be weakening and this can change the previously believed fate of our universe to be the “Big Crunch” instead of the “Big-Freeze” [32-34].

Cosmic events before Resurrection

Many cosmic events are expected to occur before the Resurrection. The following verses present some of these events along with their possible scientific parallels.

Merging of the Sun and the Moon

As was said in the introduction, in about 5 billion years from now the red giant Sun becomes so large that its outer boundaries will devour both the Earth and the Moon. However, in this event ***the Moon will merge with the Sun sooner than the Earth does***, because in half of its orbit around the

Earth, Moon is closer to the Sun than the Earth. In the meantime, during and even before this merging process, *oceans of the Earth will boil and evaporate and its mountains will lose their firmness and become scattered*. Life on Earth, in any of its forms, has long disappeared before these happenings, which can mean that by this time Armageddon must have happened (39:68).

In the following verse, merging of the Sun and Moon is indicated as one of the forthcoming events towards the Resurrection Day:

و جمع الشمس والقمر 75:9

and the Sun and the moon will be joined together, 75:9

Mountains

In the course of Earth's gradual annihilation by the approaching red giant Sun, mountains will be moved and scattered:

وإذا الجبال نسفت 77:10

and when the mountains will be blown away as dust, 77:10

وإذا الجبال سيرت 81:3

when the mountains shall be set in motion, 81:3

وتكون الجبال كالعهن 70:9

and the mountains will become like dyed tufts of wool, 70:9

Earth waters

The approaching red giant Sun will demolish Earth's atmosphere and will boil and evaporate ocean waters:

وإذا البحار سجرت 81:6

When the oceans boil over with a swell; 81:6

Sun and other Stars

All stars in the universe (including the Sun) will eventually cool and turn dark [12]:

فإذا النجوم طمست 77:8

So when the stars are put out, 77:8

وإذا النجوم انكدرت 81:2

When the stars fall, losing their luster; 81:2

إذا الشمس كورت 81:1

When the Sun is shrouded in darkness, 81:1

The sky

It was said before, that the Arabic word السماء or “sky” has been used in the Quran with a range of meanings from Earth’s atmosphere to the entirety of the universe. The following verses may be describing obliteration stages of the Earth’s atmosphere during its encounter with the red giant Sun. But on a grand universal scale, these verses could also be hinting at changes in the fabric of the spacetime in the terminal stages of a crushing universe [35]:

يوم تكون السماء كالمهل 70:8

On a Day when the heavens will be like molten brass 70:8

وإذا السماء فرجت 77:9

When the heaven is cleft asunder; 77:9

وإذا السماء كشطت 81:11

and when the sky is stripped away, 81:11

Further examples of futuristic verses in the Quran

Enormity of the universe

The common belief in the old ages was that sky is a dome with stars attached on it [35]. Verse 40:57, as was mentioned before, refers to the greatness of the universe and people’s ignorance about this fact. Verses 56:75 and 56:76, are also in agreement with our current knowledge about the enormity of the universe. *In particular, clear reference is made here to the huge astronomical distances of the stars* that even now are incomprehensible for most (measured in many billions of light years).

فلا أقسم بمواقع النجوم 56:75

وإنه لقسم لو تعلمون عظيم 56:76

So I do swear by the positions of the stars— 56:75

And indeed, it is an oath - if you could know - [most] great. 56:76

Mountains that move like clouds

وترى الجبال تحسبها جامدة وهي تمرمر السحاب صنع الله الذي أتقن كل شيء إنه خبير بما تفعلون 27:88

Now you see the mountains, thinking they are firmly fixed, but they are travelling ‘just’ like clouds. ‘That is’ the design of Allah, Who has perfected everything. Surely, He is All-Aware of what you do. 27:88

To those on Earth, mountains look motionless with respect to the ground, but if mountains are moving it means that the ground (Earth) should also be moving! The similitude between mountains and clouds (Fig.5) has been used in the Quran, perhaps because they both are large and comparable in size, and both move swiftly and quietly.

Verse 27:88 is a clear statement of the fact that, the Earth moves, contrary to the general belief up until four centuries ago, that it does not!

Fig.6 “Mountains moving like clouds” (Himalaya) [37]

Future means of transportation

والخيل والبغال والحمير لتركبوها وزينة^٤ ويخلق ما لا تعلمون **16:8**

He also created⁷ horses, mules, and donkeys for your transportation and adornment and He creates what you do not know. **16:8**

This verse starts by reminding means of transportation in the era of Quran’s revelation, but suddenly and without any obvious connection, “unknown things” are added which will be created later. **Considering the “transportation context” of this verse, the reference should almost certainly be made to the future means of transportation (trains, cars, planes, etc.).** Interestingly, not until about 200 years ago, when the first steam train was operated [38], there were any other forms of transportation other than those mentioned in the beginning of this verse (horses, mules, etc.). Another interesting point in this verse is introduction of God as “The Inventor” of the new means of transportation, which in general can mean that all human inventions are by divine inspirations.

Crossing the boundaries by acquiring knowledge

يا معشر الجن والإنس إن استطعتم أن تنفذوا من أقطار السماوات والأرض فانفذوا^٤ لا تنفذون إلا بسلطان **55:33**

O company of jinn and mankind, if you are able to pass beyond the regions of the heavens and the Earth, then pass. You will not pass except by authority [from Allah]. **55:33**

The Arabic word سلطان has been used in several other verses in the Quran and has often been translated to “authority” or “permission”, however, it has also been equated to “knowledge” [39]. A contemporary interpretation of this verse for humans can then be: **All kinds of transportations (on Earth, in the air, in the space, etc.) will be possible, but only by gaining the relevant knowledge.**

Summary and Conclusion

In this article many verses were chosen from the Quran as examples to show how they can match current human knowledge. These verses were termed futuristic, because they seem to reflect currently accepted scientific veracities, unknown at the time of Quran's revelation. Fundamental physical concepts such as homogeneities of time and space, relativity of time, along with recently discovered dark matter and dark energy, have been shown as examples of such futuristic notions in the Quran.

Defensive mechanisms of the planet Earth against the outer space threats such as cosmic rays and meteors seem to have been noted in the Quran, although not directly, but in a metaphoric language. The word "day" and a number of its possible meanings in the Quran, have been shown through several examples. In verses 32:5 and 70:4, "day" suggests a relativistic concept, while in verses 41:9 and 50:38, it proposes a fixed length of time used to measure creation times of both the universe and the Earth. It is amazing that in terms of the age ratios of the universe and the Earth, Quran's stated ratio agrees well with the scientifically accepted value 3. The 4 unequal-length "days" mentioned in verse 41:10, may well be representing 4 major eons of the Earth in Geology.

Birth of the universe as expressed in the Quran, appears to be in exact agreement with the accepted Big Bang theory. But contrary to the current belief of the astrophysicists, Quran predicts a closed universe for which supporting evidence seems to be emerging. In addition, Quran may also be hinting at some sort of universal rotation during the course of cosmic evolution. Termination of the present universe is said in the Quran to be followed by another Big Bang leading to the birth of a new universe. According to the Quran, at some stage of its development, the Resurrection Day should ensue in this newborn universe. The cosmic events up until Resurrection, as are described in the Quran, seem to be in agreement with the current knowledge.

Invention of new means of transportation and possibility of humans crossing beyond "boundaries of the Earth and space" is also indicated in the Quran, but only via mastering the relevant (scientific and technical) knowledge.

In the end, it should be emphasized again that this article is speculative in nature and does not intend to conflict with traditional interpretations.

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